

TEACHING GRAMMAR INSTRUCTION FOR PRIMARY SCHOOL LEARNERS

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***Abstract.** It is essential to teach students grammar instruction from beginning level for several reasons. In this article will be overviewed grammar units that are necessary to teach in primary school and what they include and why they should be covered on this stage. Furthermore, in this work will be explored what challenges teachers might face while teaching grammar for primary school learners, and how struggle with these challenges. In addition, in this article will be examined traditional and modern methods and techniques for teaching grammar in primary school. In this article will be provided opinions and findings of famous methodists of Uzbekistan and other countries.*

***Key words.** grammar instruction, grammar skill, active and passive grammar minimum, productive skill, grammar constructions, native language influence, cultural background, inductive and deductive presentation of grammar.*

Introduction. Grammar instruction plays crucial role in formation of communicative competence, and owing to this it is necessary to teach students to use grammar instruction properly from the very beginning stages. While teaching grammar teachers might face several difficulties, which can be connected with impact of native language or with cultural or psychological background of a student. In order to avoid these challenges it is essential to use modern and traditional techniques while teaching grammar for primary school learners

Grammar units that are taught in primary school

According to Sakaeva [5, p 67] the main purpose of teaching grammar in primary school is to develop students' grammatical skills as one of the most important components of productive skills. Grammar is one of the most important

means of language acquisition. Teaching grammar of a foreign language means to form mechanisms specific to that language, and in such a way that students develop certain grammatical knowledge which should be not only learned by heart, but also used “in working order”

According to Solovova E. N. [1, p 101], there are two types of grammar minimum: active and passive. For primary school learners active grammar minimum should be taught. Difference between active and passive minimum is that active grammar minimum is used while productive activities, and passive grammar minimum is used while reading or listening for better comprehension of material. As Galskova writes in her work [3, 147], active grammar minimum is about the formation of productive grammatical skills, for example: to form grammatical constructions, to choose and use grammatical forms properly depending on the communication situation, to vary the grammatical constructions when the communicative situation is changing, to formulate a grammatical rule based on a diagram or table, to distinguish the grammatical forms of oral and written texts.

Challenges in teaching grammar for primary school learners

While teaching grammar of foreign language to primary school learners, teacher might face several challenges. For example, influence of native language, psychological problems, linguistic and cultural background, poor engagement of students, moreover might be a situation that in one group there are students with different language levels. In opinion of J. Jalalov [2, 151] teaching grammar mechanisms of speech must be fulfilled by taking into account the mother tongue of students from the one side and secondly by overcoming negative influence of mother tongue to the foreign language speech process. Grammar rules should be explained in mother tongue, where the meaning of grammar cases and their usage are expressed for better understanding of students, also examples or linguistic alternatives connected with native language should be provided. Furthermore, as it

is written in work “Modern methods of teaching foreign languages” [4, 28], it is more interesting for students to learn language through real life situations with using of authentic materials, that’s why it is recommended for teachers to use role plays and games to overcome challenge with engagement of students. To overcome psychological challenges (for example fear of using foreign language) it is also advised to use games which will be not only beneficial, but also funny and will create friendly atmosphere in the classroom

Methods and techniques for teaching grammar in primary school

For teaching grammar instruction for primary school different techniques and methods can be used. As J. Jalalov mentions in his book [2, p 148] presentation of grammar material happens inductively or deductively. Inductive presentation begins from example and transfers to abstraction; deductive one presents a rule (or a speech pattern) then practices examples. For teaching grammar of foreign language both ways should be used.

There are different approaches for teaching grammar, which are divided into traditional and modern. Traditional method is based on teaching grammar and then doing grammar exercises in written form. But many scientists suggest that this way of teaching is old, and modern approaches should be used. As it writes in book “Modern methods of teaching foreign languages” [4, p 5] communicative method, which is based on using new grammar rules in communicative situations, should be used while foreign language lessons. Also in this book [5, p 28] is written about usage of real life situations, which can be simulated while role plays conversations, games or scenes.

For better comprehension of material is suggested to use PPP (Present Practice Produce) technique, where on every stage different types of exercises can be used

Conclusion. Grammar instruction is essential for developing communicative competence, so it is important to teach students how to use grammar effectively

from the very beginning. Teachers may have various challenges while teaching grammar, which could be related to the influence of a student's native language or their cultural and psychological background. To overcome these challenges, it is crucial to use both modern and traditional methods when teaching grammar to primary school students.

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